

EFFECTIVENESS OF PUNJAB EDUCATION AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE INITIATIVE (PEELI) TRAINING PROJECT IN PUNJAB, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

The study aimed to assess the effectiveness of the PEELI training initiative on the learning outcomes of public school teachers in Punjab, Pakistan. The British Council's effort in Punjab, in partnership with the Directorate of Staff Development (DSD), aligned with the GoP's transition to English as its medium of instruction. The current study comprised all primary school teachers and principals in the Sargodha district. This study employed all four levels of the Kirkpatrick model. For this objective, two surveys, one for teachers and one for heads of schools, were developed using Kirkpatrick's (2009) criteria and British Council assessment tools. All stakeholders, including qualified teachers and heads, provided extremely favorable and encouraging feedback. The learning level findings revealed that all of the participants gained new information and abilities from the PEELI program. Following this instruction, their attitudes improved, as well as their trust and devotion levels climbed. The level four findings showed extremely encouraging results. The level of instruction and learning was improved. Students as well as instructors both loved their classes, and dropout rates were reduced. In a nutshell, this training program may benefit all stakeholders greatly, and public educational institutions can only produce positive outcomes if trainees get assistance, reinforcement, and incentive, as well as being closely assessed for training transfer.

INTRODUCTION

A nation's achievement and progress are best measured by its educational system. The instructor is the core of this organizational structure, since their abilities and creativity define overall quality and worth. Many studies in Pakistan show that teachers have a substantial impact on students' learning techniques and perceived quality. It is well acknowledged as the vast majority of public sector primary school teachers in Punjab lack a firm comprehension of language talents in English and hence are unable to communicate them to their

students. Teachers' working circumstances and societal expectations are becoming increasingly demanding. They try to provide students with a diverse set of abilities that will enable them to take their place in a quickly changing workplace; this heightens the need for more competence-centered teaching techniques, as well as an increasing emphasis on student success. Today's instructors possess a diverse set of teaching abilities and capacities. To obtain great results, teachers create advanced teaching

techniques through periodic training programs (Khan & Haseeb, 2017).

According to Zein (2017) stated that since it is a universal truth, mainly instructors can change students' minds in a thought-provoking way. One may argue that instructors are a transformative force in society. Several professors serve the nation. It has been observed that the educational system is insufficient. The purpose of English training is to have a long-term influence on both the current and future trainings. In-service training is primarily aimed at teachers, and the same synchronization is then extended to learners, who pick their impact on society.

Statement of the Problem

It is well acknowledged that the majority of public sector elementary school teachers in Punjab lack a thorough command of English language skills and hence are unable to communicate them to their students. The Punjab government collaborated with the British Council to launch the Punjab Education and English Language Initiative (PEELI), which assists teachers in teaching their courses in English. Regardless of the efforts made, the key issue that must be addressed is the amount to which the established English language skills objectives have been met and how far these planned English language abilities have been achieved.

Significance of the Study

The study sought to identify and comprehend trainee instructors' evolving expectations, particularly when they employ their newly developed English language abilities in their teaching. The findings will also aid administrators at all levels by giving clearer policy recommendations for launching initiatives to increase instructors' and learners' English ability.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The British Council and the Punjab Government collaborated on the Punjab Education and English Language Initiative (PEELI) (Naz et al., 2020). The project aims to train about 300,000 teachers throughout all districts of Punjab in order to increase their pedagogical abilities and English language proficiency.

However, Imran et al. (2024) conducted an empirical analysis that revealed further systemic concerns,

including overcrowded classrooms, restricted access to contemporary amenities, and certain instructors' lack of professional certificates. The study showed that many primary school teachers receive no specific language education, and that some non-English background instructors are appointed to teach language lessons. This gap emphasizes the need for higher hiring standards as well as better professional development programs.

Whereas, Mushtaq (2021) underlines the significance of tailoring training materials to the cultural and social contexts of Punjab schools in order to increase applicability. PEELI's review is supported by a larger body of literature on teacher preparation in disadvantaged nations.

As stated by Almulla (2020), teamwork and activity-driven solutions, such as those promoted by PEELI, boost student participation, but must be carefully implemented to maintain long-term benefits. The PEELI training initiative has significantly improved the academic skills and English language ability of Punjabi elementary school teachers. The child-friendly idea and cascade approach to training improved school performance and pupil participation.

According to Stufflebeam and Shinkfield (2007), evaluation is a structured method of finding, gathering, analyzing, and using qualitative and analytical data to determine a product's value, significance, authenticity, practicality, safety, relevance, or equality. The efficiency of a training program is typically evaluated at the end of a lengthy project period, which might last one, two, or three years.

These evaluations are frequently carried through a team who have ample opportunity for gathering data, make conclusions, and recommend next steps. Certain participants might not absorb evaluation and take it negatively, yet evaluation is never meant to be a negative experience. We need to create an ideal environment in which everyone works together and uses the evaluation process to improve educational quality.

Kirkpatrick and Kirkpatrick (2006) defined certain objectives for assessing training courses. He stated that evaluation helps choose either to carry on or quit training programs and provides ideas on how to enhance training programs in the future. The

Kirkpatrick Model is a well-known method for evaluating the efficacy of training activities. It separated evaluation into four stages: reaction, learning, behavior, and results. This method assists firms in determining how well training programs accomplish their objectives and identifying areas for improvement.

It is the most often used evaluation method among practitioners and researchers globally. Its practicality, simplicity, and applicability to any organizational setting, either business or education, making it a genuinely distinctive framework as presented here.

Figure 1: Kirkpatrick Model, (Kirkpatrick and Kirkpatrick, 2006)

Kirkpatrick's four-tier framework of training evaluation in education is consistent with educational success. Changing the organization's training assessment process might yield particular metrics for success (Alsalamah & Callinan, 2021).

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a survey (descriptive) research methodology. A framework was developed to get reliable information from stakeholders, which included an explanation of the overall population, sampling tool development, refinement, data collection procedure, and data analysis. The population consisted of all head teachers and Primary School Teachers (PSTs) in Punjab province. Due to time and resource restrictions, accessible participants in Sargodha district were included in sample.

The study's participants were selected using a multistage sampling procedure. The first stage included randomly picking 28 Marakiz from a total of

116. They were then divided into two groups: 14 men (7 rural/7 urban) and 14 women (7 rural/7 urban). Ten schools were selected at random from each Markaz, comprising all elementary and stand-alone primary schools. Heads and two instructors from every one of the 28 marakiz were designated. Survey methods are frequently used to evaluate and quantify participants' emotions and opinions (Ponto, J. 2015). Two questionnaires were created to collect data on the responses, learning, on-the-job behavior, and results of primary school teachers who had undergone PEELI training, in addition to the head teachers of their institutions. The questionnaires were designed following a comprehensive review of the literature. They were developed employing a Likert scale of five points. The instrument was created to gather data on the general thinking habits of teachers and their brains. Both surveys used all four levels of the Kirkpatrick model, along with their subsections.

Figure 2: The new world of Kirkpatrick model (Kirpatrick Partners 2010-2012)

The values of Cronbach’s alpha for overall questionnaire (60 items) were as under:

Variables	N	α value
1. Teachers’ Questionnaire	560	0.891
2. Heads Questionnaire	280	0.957

Values (0.891 and 0.957) in the above mentioned table showed that the questionnaires were highly reliable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

No	Description	SD %	D %	(SD+D) %	U %	A %	SA%	(A+SA) %	Mean	Level
1	Reaction	2.71	13.4	16.1	16.1	38.7	29.0	66.6	3.78	High
2	Learning	0.7	5.9	6.6	10.7	56.5	26.1	82.6	4.03	High
3	Behaviour	3.0	17.4	20.4	7.8	48.2	23.5	71.7	3.72	High
4	Results	2.9	16.9	19.9	10.9	47.2	22.0	69.2	3.68	High
Overall average Percentages and Mean scores		2.3	13.4	15.8	11.4	47.7	25.2	72.5	3.80	High

Table 1: Teachers’ responses regarding all four Levels of Kirkpatrick Model

Table 1 displays overall basic statistics regarding elementary level public school teachers’ perceptions about PEELI training on all four levels of Kirkpatrick Model. It reveals that the majority of teachers reacted favourably and enjoyed the PEELI training at high level of mean score (3.78).

They reported that their overall learning was enhanced at high level of mean score (4.03). It shows that their knowledge was enriched, they gained innovative skills and their attitudes were positively changed after PEELI training.

They also reported a high mean score (3.72) for applying all newly acquired skills on the job. It is encouraging to see the implementation of training in real-time classrooms.

A high mean score (3.68) also shows that elementary level public school teachers are expecting more positive results due to their participation in PEELI training. In a nutshell, based on the high mean scores and percentages, the researcher concluded that elementary level public school teachers responded positively towards to PEELI training project.

Table 2: Heads’ responses regarding all four Levels of Kirkpatrick Model

Table 2 displays overall basic statistics regarding elementary level public school heads’ perceptions about PEELI training on all four levels of Kirkpatrick Model. It reveals that the majority of heads reacted favourably and they perceive that their teachers enjoyed the PEELI training at high level of mean score (3.78). They reported that their teachers' overall learning was enhanced at high level of mean score (4.03). It also endorses that their knowledge was enriched, they gained innovative skills and their attitudes were too positively changed after attending PEELI training. They also reported a high mean score (3.72) for applying all newly acquired skills on the job. This is heartening to note implementation of training in real time classrooms. A high mean score (3.68) also shows that elementary level public school heads are expecting more positive results owing to their participation in PEELI training. In a nutshell, based on the high mean scores and percentages, the researcher concluded that elementary level public school heads responded positively towards to PEELI training project.

Correlation Results on all Four Levels of Kirkpatrick Model

Table 3: Correlation among Teachers on four levels evaluation (n=560)

		Reaction	Learning	Behaviour	Results
Reaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.526**	.327**	.409**
Learning	Pearson Correlation	.526**	1	.505**	.403**
Behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.327**	.505**	1	.192
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000		.053
Results	Pearson Correlation	.409**	.403**	.192	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.053	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 3 shows that inferential statistics were used to determine correlations, bivariate coefficients, and Pearson's r parametric test of correlation. Except for behaviour, three factors were found to be associated. Six associations were detected and analyzed. The results demonstrate that the correlation between 'Reaction and Learning' was (r =.526), indicating a substantial and positive linear association. The correlation between 'Reaction and Behavior' was substantial (r =.327), as was the correlation between

'Reaction and Results' (r =.409), indicating a statistically meaningful association. The correlation between 'Learning and Behavior' was (r=.505), indicating a statistically significant association. The correlation between 'Learning and Results' was likewise statistically significant (r =.403). Finally, the correlation between 'Behavior and Results' was in the low range (r =.050), indicating no meaningful association.

Table 4: Correlations among Heads on four levels evaluation (n=280)

		Reaction	Learning	Behaviour	Results
Reaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.757**	.603**	.529**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
Learning	Pearson Correlation	.757**	1	.717**	.821**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
Behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.603**	.717**	1	.621**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
Results	Pearson Correlation	.529**	.821**	.621**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 displays the inferential statistics consisting Pearson's r parametric test of correlation and bivariate coefficients. It found that all four factors connected with one another. Six associations were detected and analyzed. The results demonstrate that the correlation between 'Reaction and Learning' was (r =.757), indicating a highly significant and positive linear connection. The correlation between 'Reaction and Behavior' was substantial (r =.603), as was the correlation between 'Reaction and Results' (r =.409), indicating a statistically meaningful association. The

correlation between 'Learning and Behavior' was (r=.717), indicating a statistically significant association. The correlation between 'Learning and Results' was likewise statistically significant (r =.821). Finally, the correlation between 'Behavior and Results' was (r = 621), indicating a substantial link.

PEELI Training helped teachers improve their English language skills. The efficacy is evaluated in terms of instruction approaches, content, trainee viewpoint, trainer technique, activity-driven training,

and approach to teaching all English language competencies.

Huang, Shenhui Cindy Huang (2001) examined that a language instructional method training course influenced the learning of pupils, conduct, mindsets, nervousness, and capability. The study demonstrates that language-learning methods may be taught and used by learners during their language acquisition process. However, this study finds that trainers and teachers who did not receive enough training had no substantial improvements in language skills or learning motivation. This study is consistent with current studies since it yields same results. The initiative has created a collaborative learning environment that promotes active learner involvement and offers a friendly activity-driven, pupil-centered strategy for effective and quality teaching. According to Mushtaq, T. (2021), PEELI has helped to build and polish the teaching skills of Punjab government instructors, resulting in higher quality instruction in the classroom and improved student learning results. He went on to say that the trainees are confident in recommending the PEELI training initiative to other instructors, which would bring an entirely novel aspect to their educational experience. Most importantly, their English language skills have improved to some extent. It is a goal-oriented and well-planned training. Including suggestions for future tries can improve the interactive experience. Trainees actively recommend this program to other instructors, resulting in an effective experience overall. The new investigation reached roughly similar conclusions.

CONCLUSION

Evaluation of the PEELI project based on The Kirkpatrick model indicated that the program focused on shifting teachers' teaching practices. Training helped them develop their problem-solving and critical thinking skills, and they also learned the development of courses and evaluation. Training, on the other hand, altered primary teachers' teaching strategies and improved their pedagogical abilities. Training transformed the teaching approaches of both primary teachers and trainers. They have begun implementing a child-centered approach and participatory learning in the classroom. For the training initiative to be implemented successfully,

primary teachers should receive ongoing professional development and have a follow-up system in place. Furthermore, consistent departmental policy, a methodical methodology, and effective internal and external monthly review may all contribute to the project's success. Most trainers and primary teachers recommend continuing professional development and a follow-up method to ensure continuous progress in PSTs. The majority of the teachers agreed that the training improved their students' performance, while some saw no significant effect. PEELI training has helped educators improve their classroom teaching skills. The instructors had the opportunity to use what they learned throughout the training in their classrooms. It offers an interactive learning environment centered on all four language skills. More focus is placed on lowering teacher speaking time, utilizing readily available classroom tools such as A/V aids, and stressing communication abilities as well as time management.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. It is recommended that the School Education Department, in partnership with the QAED, completely redesign the system of accountability for trained staff. Classroom observations must be undertaken, and all promotions must be tied not only to trainings but also to the use of such trainings on the job.
2. This study indicated that organizations shouldn't consider the culmination of training as an end of the learning process. It must be followed by on-the-job facilitation, performance reviews, conversations, classroom practice observation, and timely feedback to support transfer.

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